

INSTITUTE FOR RESEARCH AND COMMUNITY SERVICE
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RESEARCH ETHICS APPROVAL
No. 002/WM.H9/LPPM/SKKEP/VIII/2025

The Institute for Research and Community Service (LPPM) of Widya Mandira Catholic University (UNWIRA), acting as the UNWIRA’s Research Ethics Committee (KEP), has carefully reviewed the application for research ethics approval and its attachment submitted by:

Researcher’s name : Maria Augustin Lopes Amaral
NIDN : 0805079302
Study Program : Management
Faculty : Economics and Business
University : Widya Mandira Catholic University
Research Title : **The Impact of Green Advertising and the Mediating Role of Perceived Credibility on Consumers’ Purchase of Lontar-Based Products in Indonesia**

This study received ethical approval from the Research Ethics Committee of the Institute for Research and Community Service (LPPM), Widya Mandira Catholic University (UNWIRA), Indonesia. The approval was granted under Ethical Approval No. 002/WM.H9/LPPM/SKKEP/VIII/2025 on 5 August 2025.

The Research Ethics Committee (KEP) of UNWIRA reviewed the research proposal entitled “*The Impact of Green Advertising and the Mediating Role of Perceived Credibility on Consumers’ Purchase of Lontar-Based Products in Indonesia*” and determined that the study is ethically acceptable. The researcher, Maria Augustin Lopes Amaral, is a senior lecturer at Widya Mandira Catholic University and conducted the study in accordance with applicable ethical standards.

Kupang, 18 August 2025

Head of LPPM UNWIRA,

Dr. Maximus M. Taek, M.Si